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Title: SOP to assemble and disassemble the API source (EASY-Max NG) and clean the interface components (ion sweep cone, spray cone, ion transfer tube and O-ring) of Orbitrap Fusion.

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IMPORTANT

- Clean the inlet components prior to calibration or batch acquisition by MS.
- Use a new pair of lint- and powder-free gloves before starting each removal and cleaning.
- Use UCL/MS grade methanol and water (Biosolve Chimie SARL), formic acid (p.a., Fluka).
- To manipulate or disassemble the API source and interface components, place the MS to Off Mode.
- Make sure that you do not introduce any scratches or surface abrasions by using inappropriate tools or handling the API source and interface components.
- Make a note about cleaning the API source interface components of MS to Logbook.
- SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific SII for Xcalibur 1.8.0.530, Orbitrap Fusion Tune 4.2.4321

To prepare the API source interface

1. Check there is no flow running to the API source of MS, if yes:
 - a) set the divert valve to waste (1-6 position) in Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application (Tune window), OR
 - b) turn off the Vanquish Duo LC pumps via Direct Control.
2. In the Tune window, place the MS to Off Mode.
3. Unscrew the tubing via ferule connecting the divert valve to the grounding union. After the API source cools to room temperature, remove it from the MS by unlocking the levers on both sides (Figure 1).

External surface of the spray insert, API source and the entry of ion transfer tube can become hot enough to burn your skin therefore wait until cool down to room temperature before touching them.

Figure 1 The API source housing of the MS

To remove the ion sweep cone and the ion transfer tube with rounded entry (D.I.S., PN 70005-20606)

Make sure you don't accidentally lift the release lever located at top of the API source which will vent the MS!

1. Remove the ion sweep cone by grasping its outer ridges and pulling it off smoothly.
2. Align the flat edges of custom removal tool with the flat edges on exposed tip of the ion transfer tube and rotate the tool counterclockwise. When the ion transfer tube is free of the spray cone use the hook (flat edges) on tool to pull it out of the API source interface. Remove and inspect the O-ring located behind the ion transfer tube.

Figure 2 Showing API source interface components with release lever highlighted in red

To clean the spray cone and O-ring

1. Soak lint-free tissue (e.g., Kimwipes) in 50:50 methanol/water solution and clean outside surface of the spray cone. If necessary, replace or clean the O-ring with methanol.

To clean the ion sweep cone

1. Clean the ion sweep cone with lint-free tissue soaked in 50:50 methanol/water solution. Sonicate it in 50:50 methanol/water solution (80 mL methanol + 80 mL water) in clean 250 mL beaker for 15 mins.
2. Sonicate the component in water for 15 mins and then sonicate it in methanol for 15 mins.
3. Let it air-dry for 15 mins on a clean surface at aluminium foil in hood.

To clean the ion transfer tube

1. If there is extreme contamination, follow the steps below. If not skip it and start with step 2.
 - a) Sonicate the ion transfer tube in 10% solution of Liquinox in water.
 - b) Rinse it with water and then force a strong stream of water through the orifice for 2 mins.
 - c) Sonicate it in water for 30 mins.
 (OR) Use alumina powder and wet lint-free tissue swab to smoothly remove contamination.
2. Sonicate the component in 50:50 methanol/water solution containing 20% formic acid (50 mL methanol + 50 mL water + 20 mL formic acid) in a clean 250 mL beaker for 15 mins.
3. Sonicate the component in water for 15 mins and then sonicate it in methanol for 15 mins.
4. Let it air-dry for 15 mins on a clean surface at aluminium foil in hood. Replace the ion transfer tube if the bore becomes corroded or blocked.

Figure 3 Showing the API source interface and assembling the components

To assemble the API source interface components (Figure 3)

1. Following the O-ring replacement, check that it was installed properly.
2. Carefully insert the ion transfer tube (do not bend!) by using the custom removal tool to rotate it slowly and smoothly to the final position.
3. Push the ion sweep cone back and make sure that it fits.
4. Assemble the API source housing to the MS and lock it on both sides.
5. Adjust the spray insert to position 1 or 2 for calibration or acquisition.
6. Screw the tubing via ferule connecting the divert valve (acquisition) or the syringe needle (calibration) to the grounding union.
7. Place the MS to Standby or On Mode.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Tribrid Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Getting Stared Guide and Hardware Manual.